

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D2.5 Healthy Living Ecosystems Synergies Report

Collaborative mechanisms between the quadruple helix

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Executive Summary

The deliverable 2.5 is the final one of the second work package, that follows the overall goal to generate synergies about the need to create **Col-laboratories** including social innovation actors. In this sense, the following document will first give an overview of how the INTEGER project operates in three European pilot regions and how information on creating resilient and more social ecosystems has been generated from a European perspective (chapter 2). In the following (chapter 3), the main aim is to outline the possibilities for cooperation between various quadruple helix actors (government, industry, academia and civil society). In doing so, a series of cooperative mechanisms are presented that are beneficial to incentivise collaboration. In this context, practical examples from the pilot regions are named to understand implementation strategies from practice. The document goes on (Chapter 4) to describe the pressing issues that emerged from the work in the three INTEGER pilot regions (Krakow, Catalonia, and Hamburg) during the first year of the project. The main aim of this deliverable is to raise awareness of important social issues that need to be addressed while having the opportunity to create inspiring social innovation on crucial topics.

Symbols, Abbreviations and Acronyms

4H	Quadruple helix
Col-lab	Col-laboratori (Catalonian initiative), Col-laboratory (EU INTEGER initiative)
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
D	Deliverable
ESCO	European Standard Classification of Occupations
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

1.1 Interconnecting 4 helix Innovation ecosystems in European regions

There are approximately two million social economy enterprises in Europe, representing 10% of all businesses in Europe. Achieving the triple transition “green, digital and social” demands a paramount effort to include, in a more decisive manner, social economy enterprises, social innovators and entrepreneurs in our EU innovation ecosystems.

INTEGER, a Horizon Europe project that kicked-off on 14th-15th 2023 of February in Barcelona (Spain), addresses the following questions:

- How can we actively integrate social innovation actors in European innovation ecosystems? Or better said, how can we get social and business-driven innovators to work together?

Focused on the challenge-driven promotion of **healthy living and wellbeing**, INTEGER brings forward three innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive and integrative EU innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the ‘**Col-laboratories**’, understood these as common open houses of all kinds of innovators and entrepreneurs interested in producing new products and services that come from business- or social-oriented innovation.
- An EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory, a true **network of networks’ community** with the capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects.
- A new professional profile, the ‘**Col-lab**er’ or ‘**Col-laboratory manager**’ as a multiplying agent of change in these integrated innovation ecosystems.

To gain valuable information, so-called **Col-laborathons** (quadruple helix hackathons following the INTEGER methodology) were held in 3 EU pilot regions (Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow) to foster social innovation Minimum Viable Products and services and upscale them throughout Europe by applying and testing the INTEGER 4H comprehensive model.

By facilitating **business-driven** and **social-driven innovations**, INTEGER seeks to accelerate new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, groundbreaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable 2.5 is the final one of the second work package, that follows the overall goal to generate synergies about the need to create a **Col-laboratory** including social innovation actors. In this sense, the following document will first give an overview of how the INTEGER project operates in three European pilot regions and how information on creating resilient and more social ecosystems has been generated from a European perspective (chapter 2). In the following (chapter 3), the main aim is to outline the possibilities for cooperation between various quadruple helix actors (government, industry, academia and civil society). In doing so, a series of cooperative mechanisms are presented that are beneficial to incentivise collaboration. In this context, practical examples from the pilot regions are named to understand implementation strategies from practice. The document goes on (Chapter 4) to describe the

pressing issues that emerged from the work in three pilot regions (Cracow, Catalonia, and Hamburg) during the first year of the project. The main aim is to raise awareness of important social issues that need to be addressed while having the opportunity to create inspiring social innovation on crucial topics.

1.3 Synergies with other deliverables

This deliverable D2.5 follows the second project objective of generating synergies about the need to create a Col-laboratory on healthy living innovations. In this context, the report tries to highlight different collaborative mechanisms with the examples from the INTEGER pilot regions. The explanation of these mechanisms, in conjunction with an overview of common societal problems identified, should highlight the importance of more cooperation regarding healthy living. In this context, the report also contributes to the overall goal of implementing a transition from the knowledge triangle to a dynamic 4 helix in order to enable the bridge from social innovation to the business market, reinforcing the relations between regional and trans-regional actors.

Further on, the contents presented are related to other deliverables of the second work package and are based on the findings from the regional partners in Catalonia, Krakow and Hamburg (see chapter 2). The practical visits to the various pilot ecosystems (deliverable D2.1 - *Inter-ecosystems hands-on visit plan*) and an insight into their stakeholders in the Col-laboration sessions (deliverable D2.2 - *Col-labarathon Report & Exploitation Plan*) were used to select the practical examples. Furthermore, the document is also related to deliverable D2.3 (*INTEGER platform guidelines*), which presents the INTEGER community working platform [theglocal.network](#). In addition, deliverable D2.4 (*Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged*) presents the process of knowledge genesis in the three pilot ecosystems.

Beyond this, D2.5 is linked to the capacity building of the third work package. For example, findings from the report are communicated within the Col-laber training, which introduces people to the professional profile of the Col-laber (deliverable D3.2 - *Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery*).

Finally, the results are related to work package 5, communication. In this context, the findings of stakeholder mapping were used as a foundation for the work.

2 European ecosystems of the INTEGER project

INTEGER creates an innovation model, the INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory model, for accelerating the integration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs in three EU pilot regions. These pilot regions are monitored to identify common problems and potentials, to initiate a European knowledge transfer and to start helping to develop more sustainable innovation ecosystems. In the following paragraph, the different pilot regions in Spain, Poland and Germany will be presented, while also giving a small insight into some of the stakeholders involved.

Figure 1 - Map indicating the three INTEGER pilot regions

2.1 Catalonia

The Colab.cat community [1] is the first step in the integration of the Triple and Quadruple innovation ecosystems in the region of Catalonia (Spain), supported by the regional digital strategy. The Col·laboratories programme was first launched in 2018 by the project partner i2CAT foundation with the support of the Generalitat, the regional government of Catalonia. i2CAT is an advanced technological centre on Internet technologies, governed by a strong alliance of digital companies, universities and regional and local public institutions. Since 2015 a unit of social innovators has connected i2CAT with a broader regional and European social entrepreneur community. This integration is the starting point of the Col·laboratory program.

The emerged **Catalonian Colab.cat** program is now a well-established initiative of the Catalan Directorate General of Digital Society integrating 3H and 4H models based on the use of advanced digital technologies to generate a universal innovation ecosystem in the region. In 2022, Colabs.cat has grown and includes three territorial col-labs: CatSud, Anoia and CatNord, and two thematic col-labs: Health and Wellbeing, and Education just under construction. The new Col·lab on Health and Wellbeing includes advanced health research centres like ISGlobal or IRSI-Caixa, the Foundation TIC Salut, the Catalan Health unit dealing with ICT policies, the municipalities of Mataró, Igualada, Vic and Vilanova i la Geltrú, communities of makers and fablabs like Malla, or Biocat, the organisation that promote the Bioregional ecosystem of Catalonia. In summary, the Colabs.cat community is showing that integration of social innovator actors into the regional innovation ecosystems is possible and beneficial, resulting in new Minimum Viable Products and Services, MVPS, like Botigues Savies (Wisdom Shops), a

new certificate of recognition and brand name of companies serving healthy products and services.

2.2 Krakow

The pilot region of Krakow (Poland) is also presenting established cooperations that get monitored within the INTEGER project. Mainly through the **Krakow Living Lab (KLL)**, which is a platform for testing innovative products and services in public environments (like streets, parks, buses, schools, hospitals and other public buildings). The open ecosystem involves hundreds of varied multi-stakeholders bringing and sharing experience and know-how on dimensions such as social innovation, innovation management, cooperation and co-creation between start-ups/SME and large enterprises, incubation and acceleration programmes, approaches to innovation (examples: Living Lab, design thinking, hackathons), branch events, product development and more. It serves as a hub for main innovation actors including public institutions, researchers (like universities), technology and knowledge transfer institutions and end-users.

The Krakow Living Lab is a joint venture of the **Krakow Technology Park (KTP)**, which is also involved in the INTEGER project and brings a business perspective. KTP serves as a leading business support organisation and is involved in several incubation and acceleration programs.

As an additional innovation player, the **Jagiellonian University (UJ)** serves as a representative of academia within the Polish pilot ecosystem (Malopolska Region) .

2.3 Hamburg

The last regional ecosystem that serves as a testing field for the INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory model is Hamburg in Germany. The potential is built around several institutions. For instance, the **Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH (GWHH)** serves as a cluster agency for the health economy that establishes and maintains a sustainable network across all areas of the healthcare industry. The GWHH network counts more than 3,000 decision-makers from all sectors of the healthcare industry [2].

As a further governmental player within the Hamburg region, the **Investment Bank Hamburg (IFB)** is supporting innovation in different ways. Founders can get assistance in developing their business model and can get financial support through different funding schemes.

Furthermore, the Hamburg ecosystem also includes actors from the industry sector. For example, the **Health Innovation Port (HIP)** of the company Phillips is a collaboration space, incubator, accelerator and knowledge platform, all in one. Several start-up companies are based in a building in Hamburg. As a committed interest group, HIP promotes cooperation between science and business in a targeted manner, thereby enhancing the visibility of North Germany as a hub and boosting the added value and innovative capacity of the region.

3 Col-laborative mechanisms across sectors for a healthy living ecosystem

The collaboration among the industry, the public sector, academia, and civil society is essential in building a solid and dynamic ecosystem to promote a healthier life based on social projects on well-being and health. The following chapter aims to highlight possible cooperation and synergy opportunities between actors of the quadruple helix. The mechanisms mentioned were identified within the three pilot regions of the INTEGER project and serve to better understand which actions can be promoted to improve cooperation in quadruple helix innovation ecosystems.

3.1 Research and Innovation Hubs

Research and innovation hubs are physical spaces or collaborative networks that bring together researchers, creatives and innovators. They aim to promote the exchange of knowledge, the transfer of technologies and collaboration between different actors like companies, educational institutions and government agencies. Hubs play a central role in the development and realisation of new ideas, helping to tackle social and economic challenges. They provide an environment that fosters interdisciplinary collaboration and the practical application of research results. Often hubs also enable professional development options for innovative ideas, giving funding opportunities to the civil society. Examples of successful collaborations stress the pivotal role of innovation hubs in overcoming barriers and leveraging enablers for fruitful partnerships [3]. By serving as vibrant spaces for cross-pollination of ideas, research and innovation, hubs exemplify potentials between industry and academia, creating a nexus where intellectual capital converges with real-world applications. Such synergies yield mutual benefits, enhancing innovation and propelling technological advancements.

Phillips Health Innovation Port (Hamburg) [4]

The Phillips Health Innovation Port (HIP) is a collaboration space, incubator, accelerator and knowledge-platform. It hosts several start-ups companies in a building in Hamburg. As a committed interest group, the HIP promotes cooperation between science and business in a targeted manner, thereby enhancing the visibility of North Germany as a hub and boosting the

added value and innovative capacity of the Hamburg region.

3.2 Professional Networks and Expert Panels

Expert Panels and Professional Networks are crucial instruments for bringing together stakeholders from business, government, academia and civil society and enabling effective collaborative processes.

Expert Panels are made up of subject matter experts who have extensive knowledge in specific areas and can provide valuable insights [5]. These panels play a central role in developing sound solutions to complex challenges.

Professional networks, on the other hand, are partnerships of (inter)national actors. They create a platform for the exchange of knowledge, ideas and resources by fostering individual or organisational connections within specific sectors or areas of expertise [6].

The strength of these mechanisms lies in their ability to integrate multiple perspectives. By bringing together expertise from different sectors, holistic solutions are developed. Business representatives bring practical insights, government members get ideas on how to define practical solutions, academics contribute research-based perspectives, and civil society ensures that community interests are considered and represented. These collaborative approaches foster innovation, improve decision-making and ultimately contribute to sustainable and inclusive development.

eHealth-Network (Hamburg) [7]

The eHealth-Network in Hamburg fosters digitisation in healthcare in Hamburg by deriving impulses for innovative technologies from other branches and markets. It's focused on bringing together actors from the government, the industry and civil society, to leverage innovative potentials. Together with the Digital Health Hub Hamburg the network supports founders and start-up companies and thus offers a place where innovative ideas can grow.

3.4 Technology and knowledge transfer

Technology and knowledge transfer is needed to identify and utilise innovation. In institutional terms, technology transfer means the private-sector or state-supported process of spreading or utilising technological innovation in a planned, time-limited manner for the economic benefit of third parties. The transfer generally takes place by means of a legal act (for instance a licence agreement) [12]. In this respect, technology transfer is crucial in order to transfer innovative development opportunities from the university setting to business environments. Hence, academic research, coupled with industry resources, guides the development of sophisticated health technologies for the benefit of the civil society. From wearable devices to telehealth solutions, this collaboration propels the healthcare landscape into an era of personalized, data-driven well-being. In the INTEGER Project, the consortium identified several examples highlighting the importance of this kind of collaborative opportunities.

University Hospital Hamburg – Eppendorf (Hamburg)

The Universitätsklinikum Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE) is one of the most important innovators in the healthcare sector in Hamburg. Innovation happens in different fields. The UKE lies emphasis on innovation and collaboration. So for instance by networks like the national autopsy network (NATON) [13] initiated by the institute for legal medicine [14], or the collaborations of the Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development (IIRVD) [15]. A lot of actions within the UKE are built upon innovation, like the 3D printing of medicines project, that also serves as a perfect example for technology transfer as it is focused on bringing 3d printer technology to pharmacies [16].

Centre for Technology Transfer (Krakow) [17]

The Centre for Technology Transfer at the Jagiellonian University in Krakow (CITTRU) has the task of identifying innovations in the university environment in developing an innovation portfolio. Its further task is to communicate with potential buyers and to promote valuable research findings and technical innovation in order to put them into use.

3.5 Public-Private Partnerships for Healthcare Access

Public-private partnerships (PPP's) for healthcare access involve collaboration between government entities and private sector organisations to improve the delivery and accessibility of healthcare services to the civil society. They mostly mobilise funds from both public and private sources, leveraging financial resources for healthcare infrastructure and services aiming to enhance their efficiency and effectiveness [18]. In this context, they often try addressing health challenges in rural areas through Initiatives like mobile clinics, community health centers, and telemedicine programs [19]. Businesses contribute not only with financial resources but also by bringing innovation and management expertise, weaving a narrative of inclusive well-being [20].

Optimedis (Hamburg) [21]

The company developed a business model on how health systems can be organised in a more effective and preventive way. It is working in different German and European regions with different systematic approaches and as well in several European innovation projects.

4 Common health related issues to emerge social innovation upon

The collaborative mechanisms mentioned in the previous chapter show various approaches to cooperation between the quadruple helix actors that were familiarised within the INTEGER project. The following chapter is concerned with presenting existing problems on the basis of which social innovations can emerge.

Social innovation is the process of creation, realisation and dissemination of new social practices in different social spheres, tackling different societal problems. It can take various forms, such as community-based projects, technology-driven solutions, or new business models focused on social impact. As a practical example for social innovation, for instance, the application "too good to go" can be named, which helps to offer leftover food from establishments at a discounted price before closing time. In this context, the usage of the app brings advantages to consumers while also tackling the societal issue of food waste [22].

This chapter aims to present you societal problems that were identified within all pilot regions of the INTEGER project. Based on this, the aim is to provide you with insights into the development of social innovations. As in the previous chapter, you will find practical examples of organisations that are already trying to innovatively counteract each of the problems described. All examples come from the three pilot regions of the INTEGER project.

4.1 Pollution

Pollution is a serious social issue as it has a direct impact on the health and quality of life of communities. People in deprived neighbourhoods are more likely to be affected by transport-related health impacts such as noise and air pollutants and have less access to healthy environmental conditions. In deprived neighbourhoods, the health impacts of environmental problems are often particularly high, negatively affecting the quality of life of their residents. In this context, exposure to air pollution, noise pollution and other environmental problems also increases social inequalities in terms of health [23].

Healthy Cities Generator (Catalonia) [24]

Healthy Cities has developed a tool to better adapt urban planning to health requirements. The developed generator can be used by decision makers to understand various factors influencing health and to identify key priorities for future urban planning. Other elements of the work include health impact assessments, research projects, the development of guidelines or criteria, the training of technicians and the creation of urban plans in favour of better and more sustainable urban design.

4.2 Ageing

An ageing society is a big health-related topic that has far-reaching effects on various areas of life and health systems. In particular, social security systems such as pensions, as well as care and health, are strongly affected, as a growing number of older people require financial and human resources. This leads to challenges in the financial stability, which in turn can have an impact on the younger generation and labour structures [25].

The ageing population also harbours challenges in the area of family structures, as there is an increased need for care and health support. Family members are faced with the task of balancing their professional and personal commitments with the additional responsibility of family members in need of care.

The social impact also extends to the perception of older people in society, where negative stereotypes of dependency and burden can lead to social exclusion. These prejudices affect the quality of life of older people and create another dimension of the social problem [26].

To summarise, the ageing society requires innovative solutions to address existing challenges and create an inclusive, supportive environment for people of all ages.

Pasios (Krakow) [27]

The Pasios program in Krakow is addressed to residents of the Krakow Municipality who are over 60 years old. It aims to improve the quality of life of this social group by promoting their physical activity, health care, education and intergenerational integration.

4.3 Nutrition and Healthy Living

The importance of nutrition and a healthy lifestyle lies in the big impact on society. Social inequality in access to healthy diets and lifestyles can lead to disparate health outcomes. People with limited access to resources often face challenges in acquiring quality food, which can contribute to diet-related health problems.

In addition, social status plays a critical role, as certain populations may have less access to education about healthy eating and lifestyles. This can lead to a vicious cycle in which socio-economic disadvantage affects health and vice versa [28].

Health problems resulting from unhealthy diets and inactive lifestyles place a burden not only on individuals, but also on the healthcare system and society as a whole. Chronic diseases that are favoured by such lifestyle habits increase the burden on the healthcare system and can lead to higher costs.

ALISON (Catalonia) [29]

In response to the growing need to transform the food system and, in particular, the promotion of healthy and sustainable food, the multi-stakeholder innovation network Alison was born. Alison aims to innovate in the promotion of healthy and sustainable food in Barcelona to make it more systemic, collaborative and decentralised.

4.4 Digital Exclusion

Digital exclusion is a serious social problem with wide effects on society. This phenomenon refers to the fact that certain population groups or individuals are disadvantaged due to a lack of digital participation. There are many reasons for this, ranging from insufficient access to digital technologies to a lack of digital skills.

Inequality through digital exclusion extends across different areas of life, such as education, employment and social interaction. People without sufficient digital access may be cut off from educational resources, have more difficult access to the labour market and are impaired in social communication [30].

Digital inclusion, on the other hand, not only enables access to information and resources, but also promotes active participation in social life. It is important because people with digital access enjoy significant advantages in our society [31].

AEMA cooperative (Catalonia) [10]

The AEMA cooperative is a non-profit organisation that among other things gives digital and administrative training to people in risk of social exclusion. In this context, AEMA cooperates with the municipality of Barcelona and helps individuals with school and social registration, the job search or providing training for achieving diverse digital qualifications. In this context they are following the goal of diminishing social exclusion.

4.5 Physical inactivity

A lack of physical activity is considered a serious social problem as it has far-reaching consequences on health. Physical inactivity is associated with an increased risk of various health problems, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes, certain cancers and non-communicable diseases (NCDs). This places a burden not only on individuals, but also on the healthcare system through high medical costs and productivity losses.

Social determinants play a crucial role as they influence access to and participation in physical activity. For instance, social isolation, insufficient resources and living conditions can limit the opportunity to participate in physical activities [32]. This exacerbates health inequalities and has a negative impact on quality of life and well-being [33].

The World Health Organisation emphasises the societal costs of physical inactivity, which manifest themselves in hidden and growing healthcare costs and productivity losses. In addition, mental health problems such as anxiety and depression can be exacerbated [34].

Overall, tackling the problem requires a holistic approach at individual, social and policy levels to minimise the health risks and promote the societal benefits of physical activity.

5 Summary and perspective

Introducing the co-creation perspective, the collaborative mechanisms outlined in Chapter 3 represent a range of cooperative initiatives involving academia, business, government, and civil society, identified within the three pilot regions of the INTEGER project. The report underscores the significant relevance and positive potential inherent in fostering stronger cooperation among these key stakeholders. This emphasis is further echoed in the practical collaboration examples provided by existing organisations in Chapters 3 and 4, highlighting the need for continued promotion of such co-creation practices.

When it comes to the implementation of some of the mechanisms mentioned (community health projects / education programmes) or tackling the mentioned health related issues, it becomes evident that having knowledge of existing funding opportunities and appropriate financing strategies is crucial. Especially in this financial context, it will be important to pick up positive approaches that can already be recognised. A trend that promotes better cooperation between the social and business worlds is for instance the increasing development of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) plans. Through reporting on environmental, social and governance aspects and the obligation to draw up CSR plans for companies, cooperation between business and social innovation is therefore also becoming increasingly important from a legal and moral perspective. In this regard the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) already obliges larger companies to report on sustainability [35].

Nevertheless, in order to make social innovations and mechanisms realisable from a micro perspective, it will also become increasingly important to use new and sustainable business models. For example, large expenses can be justified without income provided that the implementation of the developed solutions results in large savings in future healthcare costs. Such financial models can become relevant when it comes to tackling social problems with innovative ideas and getting them financed.

Regarding the health-related subjects listed in chapter 4, it is clear that there are still a lot of problems to be dealt with, but this also offers great potential for social innovation for the benefit of all. In the context of health ecosystem synergies, the presented projects exemplify a co-creative approach, showcasing collaborative efforts and synergies among diverse stakeholders and regions. The INTEGER project's pilot regions reveal a cooperative alliance involving academia, business, government, and civil society — a framework commonly known as the quadruple helix model. Here the Healthy Cities Generator in Catalonia serves as a prime example, fostering collaborative urban health planning among decision-makers. Similarly, the Pasion program in Krakow engages healthcare providers, educational institutions, and local government in an intergenerational initiative. These initiatives, interconnected across sectors and regions, underscore the significance of co-creation and synergies among academia, business, government, and civil society, contributing to holistic solutions for societal challenges within health ecosystems.

In this context, the INTEGER project wants to make a contribution. In order to use the findings of the report and make real cooperation possible, a digital community network called [theglobal.network](#) has been created, which has the potential to connect actors from different areas of society and provide contact opportunities to existing organisations and projects. If you are interested in participating in our interdisciplinary network or if you are looking for contacts

and more inspiration for your own social innovation idea, become a part of INTEGER. Simply click on the INTEGER logo or scan the QR code below to complete the registration flyer.

*Figure 2 - QR code to the membership form of
theglobal.network*

6 References

- [1] "Inici," Col·laboratori Catalunya. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://colabscatalunya.cat/>
- [2] "About the Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gwhh.de/english/>
- [3] M. O'Dwyer, R. Filieri, and L. O'Malley, "Establishing successful university–industry collaborations: barriers and enablers deconstructed," *J Technol Transf*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 900–931, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10961-022-09932-2.
- [4] "Health Innovation Port." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.healthinnovationport.de/>
- [5] K. Lee, "Civil Society Organizations and the Functions of Global Health Governance: What Role within Intergovernmental Organizations?," *Glob Health Gov*, vol. 3, no. 2, p. http://blogs.shu.edu/ghg/files/2011/11/Lee_Civil-Society-Organizations-and-the-Functions-of-Global-Health-Governance_Spring-2010.pdf, 2010.
- [6] A. G. Wilhelm, D. Woods, K. del Rosal, and S. Wu, "Refining a Professional Network: Understanding First-Year Teachers' Advice Seeking," *Teacher Education Quarterly*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 96–119, 2020.
- [7] "ehealth Hamburg | eHealth Hamburg." Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ehealth-hamburg.de/>
- [8] "Arbeitskreis Nachhaltige StadtGesundheit | Patriotische Gesellschaft von 1765." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.patriotische-gesellschaft.de/arbeitskreis-nachhaltige-stadtgesundheit>
- [9] "LIDO – Miteinander für mehr Lebensfreude vor Ort – Eine Initiative der maxingpact gGmbH." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.meinlido.de/>
- [10] "Inicio - Cooperativa AEMA." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://aema.cat/>
- [11] "Mejora el bienestar laboral en tu organización," Biwel. Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://biwel.com/>
- [12] H. Klodt, A.-K. Achleitner, and M. Klein, "Definition: Technologietransfer," *Wirtschaftslexikon Gabler*. Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de/definition/technologietransfer-50999/version-274-206>
- [13] "NATON," National Autopsy Network. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://naton.network/en/>
- [14] "UKE - Legal Medicine." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uke.de/english/departments-institutes/institutes/legal-medicine/index.html>
- [15] "UKE - Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development - IIRVD." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uke.de/english/departments-institutes/institutes/infection-research-and-vaccine-development/index.html>
- [16] "UKE - Pharmacy - 3D printing of drugs." Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uke.de/english/organizational-structure/central-areas/pharmacy/3d-printing-of-drugs/index.html>
- [17] "Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU | Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU Jagiellonian University." Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencemarket.pl/en/inventions>
- [18] World Health Organization, "Public–private partnerships for health care infrastructure and services: policy considerations for middle-income countries in Europe." Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289058605>

- [19] N. Joudyian, L. Doshmangir, M. Mahdavi, J. S. Tabrizi, and V. S. Gordeev, "Public-private partnerships in primary health care: a scoping review," *BMC Health Services Research*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 4, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s12913-020-05979-9.
- [20] PricewaterhouseCoopers, "PPPs in healthcare: Models, lessons and trends for the future," PwC. Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/industries/healthcare/publications/trends-for-the-future.html>
- [21] "OptiMedis - Management, Analytics & Research in Healthcare," OptiMedis. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://optimedis.com/>
- [22] Toogoodtogo, "Impact Report 2020," Toogoodtogo.com. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.toogoodtogo.com/en-us/initiative/campaign>
- [23] S. Khomenko *et al.*, "Premature mortality due to air pollution in European cities: a health impact assessment," *The Lancet Planetary Health*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. e121–e134, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/S2542-5196(20)30272-2.
- [24] "What we do | Healthy Cities." Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://healthycitiesgenerator.com/what-we-do/>
- [25] M. Bujard, "Die Folgen des demografischen Wandels," bpb.de. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bpb.de/shop/zeitschriften/izpb/demografischer-wandel-350/507789/die-folgen-des-demografischen-wandels/>
- [26] H. E. Restrepo and M. Rozentel, "The social impact of aging populations: Some major issues," *Social Science & Medicine*, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 1323–1338, Nov. 1994, doi: 10.1016/0277-9536(94)90364-6.
- [27] "PASIOS - Municipal Program for Social Activity and Integration of Older People for 2021 - 2025 - Kraków For Seniors." Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://dlaseniora.krakow.pl/192743,artykul,pasios.html/192743,artykul,pasios_-_gminny_program_aktywnosci_spolecznej_i_integracji_osob_starszych_na_lata_2021_-_2025.html
- [28] H. Ines, "Ernährung, Gesundheit und soziale Ungleichheit," bpb.de. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bpb.de/shop/zeitschriften/apuz/30188/ernaehrung-gesundheit-und-soziale-ungleichheit/>
- [29] "Alison," IrsiCaixa. Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.irsicaixa.es/living-lab-health/projects/alison>
- [30] A. Djouadi, J. Rössel, and A. Seifert, "Wer fühlt sich exkludiert? Zur zeitdiagnostischen Verwendung des Konzepts der sozialen Exklusion," *Köln Z Soziol*, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 361–388, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11577-021-00802-7.
- [31] B. für politische Bildung, "Digitale Inklusion – digitale Exklusion: Teilhabe in einer digitalen Gesellschaft," bpb.de. Accessed: Jan. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bpb.de/lernen/digitale-bildung/werkstatt/217272/digitale-inklusion-digitale-exklusion-teilhabe-in-einer-digitalen-gesellschaft/>
- [32] A. Delerue Matos, F. Barbosa, C. Cunha, G. Voss, and F. Correia, "Social isolation, physical inactivity and inadequate diet among European middle-aged and older adults," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 924, May 2021, doi: 10.1186/s12889-021-10956-w.
- [33] J. Z. Willey, M. C. Paik, R. Sacco, M. S. V. Elkind, and B. Boden-Albala, "Social determinants of physical inactivity in the Northern Manhattan Study (NOMAS)," *J Community Health*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 602–608, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.1007/s10900-010-9249-2.
- [34] World Health Organization, *Global action plan on physical activity 2018–2030: more active people for a healthier world*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2018. Accessed: Jan. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/272722>
- [35] "Corporate sustainability reporting - European Commission." Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/capital-markets-union-and-financial-markets/company-reporting-and-auditing/company-reporting/corporate-sustainability-reporting_en